

ISSUES OF FORMATION OF PHRASEOLOGICAL COMPETENCE IN A FOREIGN LANGUAGE

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Abstract. *The article formulates the initial use of the term "competence" in science, shows various concepts of scientists, reveals concepts such as phraseological competence, the meaning of phraseological competence in CEFR (Pan-European Competence of Foreign Language Proficiency), differences in phraseological and communicative competence of foreign language, phraseological material.*

Keywords: *competence, communicative competence, linguistic competence, phraseological competence, phraseology, phraseological material.*

The intensive development of mutually beneficial relations between our republic and foreign countries has led to an increase in the need for personnel who are fluent in a foreign language. Knowledge of foreign languages undoubtedly contributes to the development of Uzbekistan in political, economic, social and other spheres of life. The use of modern advanced technologies and techniques has a decisive impact on the intensification and modernization of the foreign language teaching system. The purpose of foreign language learning is the formation of speech skills, at the same time, the language being studied becomes a new kind of source of information. At the same time, the student not only receives, but also transmits it, using the language as not only an interlocutor, but also a cognate (owner of information). In the course of practical language learning, the student is engaged not so much in the accumulation of linguistic knowledge, as in the improvement of speech and cultural skills (competencies). Foreign language is studied on the basis of communicative activity, an integrative approach focused on personality, aimed at mastering competencies [1, p. 9].

What is competence? The most common interpretation of competence is as a set of knowledge, skills, intellectual and personal abilities necessary for the effective performance of a task of a certain level of complexity. Tracing the history of the term "competence", one can see that it originated in the 60s of the last century in the United States in training based on the training of competitive specialists in the labor market (performance-based education) [2, p. 30]. In linguistics, the term "competence", used in contrast to the terms "linguistic enterprise", "linguistic resourcefulness", "language use", was introduced by N. Chomsky. The difference between these terms is in the level of knowledge about the language and its practical application, i.e., in the speech activity of the speaker and the listener. By the mid-70s, the followers of N. Chomsky began to interpret this term as potential knowledge of the language, knowledge of the language of a true native speaker, – linguistic activity, i.e., the use of language in speech in any real situation. D. Slobin gave a clear definition of the essence of these concepts, emphasizing that a person can communicate practically, i.e., in any specific situation, if only he has the ability to speak and understand from a theoretical point of view [3, p. 23]. In a relatively short period of time, these views led to the emergence of the concept of "competence", which became the reason for the emergence of the concept of "communicative competence". From an etymological point of view, the term "competence" goes back to the Latin word "competens" (conformity, proportionality) and

has two meanings: the scope of authority of any body and official; the range of issues in which this person has knowledge and experience. The term "competence" is defined as awareness, authority in any issue, range of issues. Due to social development, many terms based on this term have emerged in various languages. In foreign publications, the ambiguous term "competence" is used, which has at least five meanings: abilities, skills, effective result of action, readiness to take action, etc. (C.Belisle, N.Chomsky, M.Linard, J.F. van Ek). Competent (French) – competent, competent; competere – to demand, comply, be fit; competence (English) – ability. The teaching methodology distinguishes between the concepts of "competence" and "competence". "Competence" is most often used to characterize the result of education, expressed in the preparedness, ability of the graduate, in real possession of the means, forms and methods of activity, in the ability to successfully cope with the tasks set. The concept characterizes such a form of combination of knowledge, skills and abilities that allows you to set certain goals and achieve them. By competence, researchers understand mainly the possession of relevant competencies by a person. According to R.P. Milrud, competence began to be studied as a personal category, and competencies became units of educational programs and constitute the anatomy of competence [2, p. 30]. It is noted that a specialist can be an expert in language (Literature), an admirer of computer literacy (Information Technology Skills), know ways to solve problems (Problem-solving skills), adaptive to any situation and innovative-minded (Flexibility and adaptability to innovations), strive for continuing education, as well as have a basic or high degree of proficiency competencies [ibid., p. 31]. Phraseology allows us to know language as a system in which linguistic constructions and structures that appeared in various historical periods and are in constant development coexist. Phraseology is closely related to the culture of speech education, so teachers working with foreign-speaking students should pay special attention to it. When studying the phraseological richness of language, it is necessary to choose phraseological material and take into account the forms, content and features of the use of phraseological units that are obvious to a native speaker, but create serious difficulties for foreign-language learners. Phraseological competence consists in the ability of students to accurately and clearly express their thoughts in the studied foreign language through phraseological units, select phraseological units in the text, interpret their meaning, analyze their speech functions, identify national and cultural differences, freely use them in their own speech, etc. As a complex linguistic phenomenon, phraseological units are a kind of intermediate unit between a word (lexico-semantic unit) and a phrase (syntactic unit) [ibid., p. 11].

Phraseological units consisting of two or more words and meaning a holistic meaning are a lexical unit of the language. Despite the fact that phraseological units consist of several words and appear as a type of phrases or sentences, they are fundamentally different from these units, which are considered to be speech units, and much closer to words as lexical units. Many characteristic properties of words are inherent in phraseological units. They, like words, have a holistic form and meaning. If the form of words consists in sounds, then the form of phraseological units consists of words. Phraseological units, like proverbs, sayings, are passed down from generation to generation. In this sense, phraseological units, reflecting the history, culture, way of life, lifestyle of a certain people, behavior of individuals, perform a cultural and informational function. Also, some of them reflect expressivity, subjective positive or negative attitude of the speaker to objects and phenomena, in some qualitative or quantitative characteristics of phenomena, objects, signs. Phraseological units occupy a special place in the lexical composition

of the language: expressing thought figuratively and accurately, they reflect various aspects of reality.

Phraseology is not only an open manifestation of reality, they characterize it, evaluate it. In terms of meaning, they are equal to an integral concept and reflect the subject, process, condition, quality, feature, method, etc., patterns that are in close relationship with the general language system.

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